

Systematisation of Synthetic Inorganic Reactions. Part-I. Electron-transfer Reactions : Possibility of introducing Name Reactions in Inorganic Chemistry

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Synthetic reactions in inorganic and coordination chemistry have not grown systematically. Since inorganic chemistry encompasses a variety of elements it is difficult to systematise those synthetic reactions. An attention has herein been focussed on the reductive reaction of higher valent metal ions with a view to generalising some synthetic routes. The concerned area is reductive nitrosylation and reductive carbonylation. It has been suggested that perhaps the introduction of name reactions, parallel to organic chemistry, may, to some extent, help in systematising inorganic reactions, specially, those used in inorganic syntheses. Some name reactions have been suggested with a hope that more and more such reactions will be reported. Besides a few interesting reductive nitrosylation and carbonylation reactions discovered by Hieber and his collaborators, two very interesting disproportionation reactions involving metal nitrosyls developed in the author's laboratories have been described in details. Kinetics and mechanistic studies of the synthetic reactions will throw more light to the concerned reaction in a bid to bring more system and logic in this still empirically growing research area.

CRITICALLY speaking, inorganic synthetic reactions are less general and more gross and empirical in their approaches than their organic counterpart. The synthetic reactions involve oxidation, reduction, disproportionation, substitution, solvolysis, generalised acid-base reaction (hence, complex formation), condensation, polymerisation, dissociation, addition, elimination and pyrolysis. The interplay of isomerisation, insertion type reactions, atom- or ion-transfer or extraction, induced or concealed electron-transfer reactions and formation of sandwiched or half-sandwiched π -complexes are actually the off-shoots of the main reaction types as categorised above. In chemistry, in general, the reaction incentives are ultimate energy minimisation via either thermal or photochemical routes. Despite some very interesting mechanistic models arising out of a remarkably thorough, intriguing, voluminous and interesting kinetic studies on certain types of substitution and electron transfer reactions, synthetic chemistry has not been much enriched and systematised. Kinetics and mechanistic studies in inorganic reactions developed out of their own glory and out of the satisfaction in understanding some very important types of inorganic reactions dealing with stereochemical and redox aspects, including their spectacular success in grossly understanding some biological electron transfer reactions. Actually a very vital support in the march of inorganic chemistry towards a science of logic from total empiricism have, no doubt, been extended by those mechanistic studies. Again, to be critical and objective, those mechanistic studies so far have dealt with some particular reaction sequences without giving any reason for their applicability in some specific systems and limitations in the others. This

is, of course, due to the fact that inorganic chemistry encompasses such a variety of elements, but the truth remains that inorganic synthesis badly needs organisation and a framework of at least qualitative principles upon which further work may be based.

Reduction of metal ions :

Reduction of inorganic ions to their lower oxidation states are affected by a variety of reagents. A general survey reveals that the reducing agents commonly used are : (i) Zn/HCl and (ii) Sn/HCl (so called 'nascent hydrogen' is supposed to be the reductant for both (i) and (ii)), (iii) SnCl₂, (iv) NaH₂PO₂ or H₂PO₂⁻ or HPO₂²⁻, (v) SCN⁻/H⁺ (Ref. 1), (vi) N₂H₄, (vii) NH₂OH, (viii) H₂S, HS⁻ and S²⁻ ions, (ix) SO₂ and SO₃⁻ ions, (x) HNO₂ and NO₂⁻ ion, (xi) NO, (xii) NOCl, (xiii) I⁻ ion, (xiv) S₂²⁻ ions (Refs. 2-4), (xv) CO[ReO₄⁻/Re₂O₇] $\xrightarrow{\text{CO}}$ [Re₂(CO)₁₀] (Ref. 5), (xvi) M/Hg (i.e. metal amalgams), (xvii) NaBH₄, (xviii) LiAlH₄, (xix) R₃A (A=P, As, Sb etc. ; Ref. 6), (xx) R₃X (X=S, Se, Te, R=alkyl or aryl groups), (xxi) Na/K benzophenone⁷, (xxii) glucose and related molecules, (xxiii) formic and oxalic acid, (xxiv) cyanide ion and isocyanides, RNC.

Hydroxylamine hydrochloride, which is otherwise a rather mild reducing agent and an interesting coordinating ligand⁸⁻¹², was known to enter in an extremely interesting course of reaction in an alkaline medium with MoO₄²⁻ substrate in the presence of CN⁻ ions. In 1896, Von der Heide and Hoffmann¹³ isolated a red-violet crystalline compound by reacting MoO₄²⁻ with NH₂OH and KCN in strong alkaline medium which they formulated as MoO₃.4KCN.NH₂OH.H₂O, on the basis

of elemental analyses. It took a long time to understand the actual molecular composition of the red-violet product. In 1948, Hieber *et al.*¹⁴ reformulated and established the actual composition of the red-violet product of Von der Heide and Hoffmann¹³ as $K_4[Mo(CN)_5NO]$, insofar as a very strong ν_{NO} vibrational band at 1455 cm^{-1} , besides the ν_{CN} vibrations at $2058, 2036$ and 2022 cm^{-1} , was found in the infrared spectrum of the red-violet crystalline product. It was shown, for the first time (the structure has subsequently been characterised by 3-dimensional X-ray crystallography by a Swedish group¹⁵) that NH_2OH in the presence of another reducing nucleophile, here CN^- , can reduce a d^0 tetraoxometalate (MO_4^{2-}) and simultaneously introduce a NO group to the low (here, formally, zero) valent metal centre. Many users of $NH_2OH.HCl$ as a mild reducing agent even may not know the above fact unless they work in reductive nitrosylation. Maintaining a parallelism with organic chemistry we can designate the reaction as **Hoffmann, Heide and Hieber Reaction**, to make the readers of inorganic chemistry conscious about this type of potentiality of NH_2OH .

To interpret the feasibility of the reductive nitrosylation reactions using hydroxylamine, Hieber *et al.*¹⁴ assumed that hydroxylamine produces NO^- in an alkaline medium in a following sequence :

The NO^- intermediate then reduces the metal ions ($NO^- \longrightarrow NO^+ + 2e$) and generates complexes containing NO^+ ligand. But, since the time Hieber *et al.*¹⁶ introduced the reaction (1),

producing tricyanonitrosyl nickelate(II) containing NO as NO^- , as a means of detecting the reactive NO^- intermediate, it has not at all been clear whether NO^- was really formed in the reaction. Veprek-Siska^{17,18} and Lunak have shown in two elegant kinetic studies that two different mechanisms are operative in the formation of $[Ni(CN)_3NO]^{2-}$, from $[Ni(CN)_4]^{2-}$ and NH_2OH , and that, most likely neither of them involves generation of uncoordinated NO^- .

Following 'Hoffmann, Heide and Hieber Reaction', Wilkinson *et al.*^{19,20} reported the syntheses of $[Cr(CN)_5NO]^{2-}$ and $[V(CN)_5NO]^{2-}$. However, the latter was first formulated as $[V(CN)_5NO]^{2-}$ and a subsequent 3-dimensional X-ray structural study by a Swedish group²¹ established that the molecule was actually trianionic. However, due to the use of only 2 to 3 moles of NH_2OH per mole of MO_4^{2-} substrates the reactions have been found to be rather sluggish, giving rise to different unconverted residues at different stages, and the ultimate yields of the nitrosyl products are quite low²².

Muller and Bhattacharyya modification :

Muller *et al.*^{23,24} and Bhattacharyya *et al.*²⁴⁻²⁶ discovered that, for reductive nitrosylation of tetraoxometallates, viz. MoO_4^{2-} , CrO_4^{2-} and OsO_4 , using $NH_2OH.HCl$ and another anionic nucleophile, viz. NCS^- , $C_2O_4^{2-}$ or N_3^- , the nitrosylation reactions (2-5),

proceed in weakly acidic or near-neutral medium (but not in alkaline medium) implying therefore that the suggested mechanism of Hieber *et al.*¹⁴ is not the only conceivable pathway of reductive nitrosylation by $NH_2OH.HCl$. Bhattacharyya *et al.*^{24-26,31} also reported that the reductive nitrosylation reaction conducted by earlier workers surprisingly used a meagre amount of $NH_2OH.HCl$ compared to that demanded by the stoichiometry of the reactions involved²² and commented that the rather sluggish and cumbersome course of the nitrosylation reaction can be overcome by using an excess of $NH_2OH.HCl$ compared to the tetraoxometalate substrates used. Using excess nitrosylating agent, this group have made a deeper study on the $MoO_4^{2-} - NH_2OH - CN^-$ reaction in alkaline medium and have shown that besides the well-known red-violet product being obtained at 80% yield, another unknown product, $K_2[Mo(NO)(CN)_5]$, considered to be a missing link in the molybdenum cyanonitrosyl compounds containing the moiety $Mo(NO)^{2+}$ ($n=1-3$), can be obtained in equally good yield. Actually they have discovered a reaction condition dependent on the alkalinity of the reaction medium whereby either exclusively $K_4[Mo(NO)(CN)_5]$ or $K_2[Mo(NO)(CN)_5]$ or both are obtained, one after the other, so that separation becomes quite easy. This group has also shown that $MoO_4^{2-} - NH_2OH.HCl - CN^-$ reaction also proceeds in slightly acidic medium affording a new product²⁴ $[Mo(NO)_2(CN)_4]^{2-}$ while similar reaction with VO_4^{3-} substrate needs an alkaline medium to afford also a new product²⁵ $[V(NO)_2(CN)_4]^{2-}$. Curiously enough, the author and his group noticed that $MO_4^{2-} - NH_2OH - NCS^-$ reaction always needs an acidic or near neutral medium for nitrosylation to take place and for isolating metal thiocyanatonitrosyl complexes, but ReO_4^- needs a highly alkaline medium for any nitrosylation reaction, irrespective of the accompanying anions which may be CN^- , SCN^- , N_3^- or even oxalate²⁶⁻²⁸.

Bhattacharyya and Bhattacharjee²⁵ and Bhattacharyya, Dasmahapatra and Roy⁴¹ reactions

In an aqueous aerobic medium, MoO_4^{2-} can be reductively nitrosylated using an excess of $NH_2OH.HCl$ and NCS^- ions in the pH range 4-4.5 generat-

ing selectively the $\text{Mo}(\text{NO})^{3+}$ (i.e. $\{\text{Mo}(\text{NO})\}^{4*}$) moiety. This had been confirmed by synthesising complexes of the types $[\text{Mo}(\text{NO})(\text{NH}_2\text{O})(\text{NCS})_4]^{2-}$, $[\text{Mo}(\text{NO})(\text{NH}_2\text{O})(\text{S}_2\text{CNET}_2)_2]$ and the isomeric $[\text{Mo}(\text{NO})(\text{NH}_2\text{O})(\text{NCS})_2(\text{L}-\text{L})]$ (LL=bipy or phen) almost in quantitative yield²⁵. However, if the same reaction is conducted at pH 5.2–5.4, a selective generation of the $\text{Mo}(\text{NO})_2^{4+}$ (i.e. $\{\text{Mo}(\text{NO})_2\}^{4*}$) occurs leading to the stereoselective synthesis of $[\text{Mo}(\text{NO})_2(\text{NHO})(\text{NCS})_4]^{2-}$ and $[\text{Mo}(\text{NO})_2(\text{NHO})(\text{NCS})_2(\text{L}-\text{L})]^{2-}$.

In the pH range 5.7–6.0, the initially formed $\text{Mo}(\text{NO})^{3+}$ (more correctly $\text{Mo}(\text{NO})\text{NH}_2\text{O}^{2+}$) species undergoes an interesting disproportionation reaction, which the author proposes to be regarded as **Bhattacharyya and Bhattacharjee Reaction**²⁵, due to its novelty and by virtue of quantitatively assessing all the products of the reaction including the gaseous ones. A very interesting reaction occurs when MoO_4^{2-} , $\text{NH}_4\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ and NCS^- are boiled in an aqueous aerobic medium in the above mentioned pH range. After 1 h the colour of the solution changes from yellow to brown and within 2 min suddenly becomes bluish green; at this stage the presence of a $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_7^{2+}$ species is detected (ir probing). The formation of the bluish green colour is complete (spectrophotometric probing) after boiling for another 1 h and the $\text{Mo}(\text{NO})_2^{3+}$ and $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_7^{2+}$ species are obtained as $(\text{Ph}_4\text{P})_2[\text{Mo}(\text{NO})_2(\text{NCS})_4]$ and $(\text{Ph}_4\text{P})_2[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_7(\text{NCS})_4]$ respectively with a relative yield of 1 : 1 (i.e. molybdenum-wise, 1 : 2). The $\text{Mo}(\text{NO})_2^{3+}$ species remains always contaminated with the oxo species, and the formation of blue green colour (Mo^{V}) in this reaction mixture is a positive indication that $\text{Mo}(\text{NO})_2^{3+}$ moiety has started to be generated. This fact, along with the relative yield of the dinitrosyl and oxo products, which have been thoroughly characterised by chemical, spectroscopic and magnetic studies, indicate that in this pH range the $\text{Mo}(\text{NO})(\text{NH}_2\text{O})^{2+}$ (i.e. containing Mo^{II} and NO^{2+}) which is the initial product of nitrosylation in all the above pH ranges (confirmed²⁵ by isolating the corresponding bipy complexes in each case after 5–10 min the reaction has started) disproportionates presumably according to the equation (6) and (7),

That $\text{Mo}(\text{NO})(\text{NH}_2\text{O})^{2+}$ takes part in the disproportionation reaction, was proved by trapping and characterising the products at regular intervals using bipy, including that present a few seconds before the appearance of the blue-green colour. Also, the mode of the disproportionation reaction was verified experimentally by repeating a relevant experiment, i.e. boiling an aqueous solution (pH

~6) of $(\text{NMe}_4)_2[\text{Mo}(\text{NO})(\text{NCS})_4]$ in a vacuum line^{25,42} and analysing quantitatively the evolved N_2O (obtained as $\text{N}_2 + 1/2\text{O}_2$ due to electron impact) and NH_3 (after boiling the ammonium salt with KOH) mass spectrometrically. However, the detailed kinetics and mechanistic studies of the above reaction are yet to be done.

Reactivity of rhenium nitrosyl compounds are equally interesting and intriguing. It is ReO_4^- , a lone tetraoxometallate ion, which undergoes a smooth reductive nitrosylation using NH_2OH in an alkaline medium as the source of NO group in the absence of any other supporting reducing agents or nucleophiles. In this process, $[\text{Re}(\text{NO})(\text{OH})_4]^-$ is formed and is isolated as Ph_4P salt (1). Interestingly, when the parent solution containing the hydroxonitrosyl anion or the compound 1 is boiled with concentrated solutions of HX ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}$ or Br), the parent (initial in the case of 1) solutions suffer a sharp colour change and from the resulting solution in each case, judicious employment of counter ion ($[\text{APh}_4]^+$, $[\text{NBu}_4]^+$) or $\text{L}-\text{L}$ (phen or bipy) gives two different species, one, containing a mono- ($[\text{Re}(\text{NO})\text{X}_4(\text{L}-\text{L})]^-$ or $[\text{Re}(\text{NO})\text{Cl}_5]^-$) and the other a di-nitrosylrhenium moiety, viz. $[\text{Re}(\text{NO})_2\text{X}_4]^-$. These can be isolated in roughly 1 : 1 molar ratio, leaving behind a lemon-green (Cl) or reddish (Br) solution⁴¹. The isolated nitrosyl products have been adequately characterised. Infrared scanning of the solution in either case shows that apart from a very small concentration of the above nitrosyl products (which obviously have a marginal solubility), the bulk is a non-nitrosyl compound which does not contain any oxorhenium moiety but does contain $\text{Re}-\text{X}$ bonds. The substance can neither be precipitated with bulky cations or anions, nor does it form any isolable derivative with $\text{L}-\text{L}$. The product may be $[\text{Re}_2\text{X}_8]^{4-}$, first obtained by Cotton *et al.*⁴³, in an aqueous solution, by polarographic reduction of $[\text{Re}_2\text{X}_8]^{2-}$, stepwise via $[\text{Re}_2\text{X}_8]^{3-}$. It could not be isolated or properly characterised by the earlier workers^{43,44} who remarked that the species was unstable and underwent easy aerial oxidation to $[\text{Re}_2\text{X}_8]^{2-}$. Bhattacharyya *et al.*⁴¹ noticed that a sharp and strong electronic spectral band is shown by the solution at ca 1 400 nm typical for $A_{2u}(\delta_u) \rightarrow B_{1u}(\delta^*)$ transition⁴⁴ in $\text{Re}-\text{Re}$ multiple bonded $\text{Re}_2\text{Cl}_8^{4-}$. The species is epr silent, as it should be, but if the HCl solution, in which the $\text{Re}_2\text{X}_8^{4-}$ seems to be quite stable, is distilled out at a reduced pressure and the residue taken up in CH_2Cl_2 , the resulting solution shows beautiful signals, signifying that the binuclear tetranegative ion is changed to ReX_6^{4-} (insofar as the $\delta_u - \delta^*$ transition disappears, and the solution becomes epr sensitive, rhenium hyperfines are commensurate with a mononuclear $\text{Re}-\text{Cl}$ complex)⁴⁵. The X -band epr spectrum in CH_2Cl_2 actually shows that each main peak of the well-defined sextet due to rhenium (^{185}Re and ^{187}Re , both with $I=5/2$) hyperfine structure is again split into a quartet due to the interaction of the unpaired electron with ^{35}Cl and ^{37}Cl (both

*The numerical superscript indicates the total number of valence electrons in metal and NO orbitals, see also Ref. 25.

with $I=3/2$); $g_{\text{solution}}=2.00$, $\langle A \rangle_{\text{Re}}$ ca 300–550 G, and $\langle A \rangle_{\text{Cl}}$ ca 60–100 G⁴¹.

Having established the composition of the non-nitrosyl compound, a reaction scheme, hereinafter be referred to as **Bhattacharyya, Dasmahapatra and Roy Reaction**⁴¹ as shown in equation (8) (A=P or As), can be drawn up to describe the proton-induced disproportionation reaction of the $\{\text{Re}(\text{NO})\}^5$ (i.e. $\text{Re}(\text{NO})^{5+}$) moiety in HX (X=Cl or Br). Thus, the reaction is essentially an electrophilic attack by H^+ (assisted by X^-) on $\{\text{Re}(\text{NO})\}^5$ which becomes facile only when strong HX solutions are used. So, this **Bhattacharyya, Dasmahapatra and Roy Reaction** is an example whereby a metal nitrosyl disproportionates and in the process besides generating new nitrosyl moieties also creates a metal-metal multiple bonded centre. A mechanistic work of

this highly interesting multi-step reaction, is very much warranted.

It was first shown by Hieber, who made many notable contributions to carbonyl chemistry, apart from the early development of nitrosylation reaction as described earlier, that iron pentacarbonyl on treatment with aqueous alkali dissolves in it to give first an yellow solution containing carbonylate anion⁴⁶, $[\text{HFe}(\text{CO})_4]^-$. The anion on acidification gives a thermally unstable gas $\text{H}_2\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_4$. Carbonylate anions have been obtained from most of the carbonyls. Some, however, do not give hydrido species on acidification, though the carbonylate ions of Mn, Re, Fe and Co certainly do. So, it would be quite proper if the conversion of metal carbonyls with aqueous alkali, to the respective carbonylate anions be termed as **Hieber Reaction**. This reaction is applicable not only to mono-nuclear, but also to the polynuclear carbonyls. Now it is well-established⁴⁷ that the carbonylate anions are obtainable in a number of ways, viz. by treating carbonyls with (i) aqueous or alcoholic alkali hydroxide or with amines, (ii) sulphoxides or other Lewis bases, (iii) by cleaving metal-metal bonds with sodium, or (iv) in special cases, by refluxing carbonyls with salts in an ether medium. However, the subsequent works all developed with the Hieber's original reaction as the nucleus.

Another discovery of Hieber is that, a seven-electron reduction via carbonylation is possible on a suitable substrate as described by reaction (9).

A parallel reaction is not yet known but seems quite possible if proper attention is paid in the reaction of tetraoxometallates with CO. The above reaction may be described as **Hieber and Fuches Reaction**⁶.

Another person who dominated the field of inorganic and coordination chemistry for more than sixty years is P. Ray. Long back a recimisation mechanism of tris chelates had been assigned after his name, the rhombic twist mechanism, also known as Ray and Dutt twist⁴⁸ mechanism. However, one of Ray's most spectacular contribution in coordination chemistry is the stabilisation of silver(III) as its ethylene dibiguanide complex (cationic) via oxidation of silver(II) using $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$. Such reactions⁴⁹ should be assigned to the name of Ray and his collaborators. The present author leaves this area for more appropriate persons to take up.

I have only tried to start the ball rolling in an attempt to attract the world attention for the systematisation of synthetic inorganic reactions with a hope that many authors will be provoked to contribute in this area. Arguments and counter-arguments will be there, many reactions will be repeated by different research groups who will possibly throw more light on the reactions or many suggested reactions will simply melt. Truth will prevail at last and we shall get some generalised reactions in inorganic chemistry as a means to systematise the inorganic reactions. Empiricism in inorganic chemistry and finding logic and basic science in it is a romantic area of research. Will not the area be illuminated along with its approach roads if the systematisation is really made possible?

A possible counter-argument may be that the introduction of names of discoverer will not bring out basic science from empiricism. The argument sounds logical. But if we think of the problem stepwise, the first step is to bring many inorganic reactions under a singular name reaction, many more to another such and to know the mechanism of the reactions. This is systemisation. When system will prevail, we can forget the names and instead more meaningful approaches should be invoked. Organic chemists are now trying to find ways and means to do this, since they have a time-tested armory of systematically grown reaction categorisation in their hands. Inorganic chemistry is now undergoing its second renaissance, and is really an exciting field of research. But is it not true that we are at least half a century back compared to the development of organic chemistry so far as systematisation is concerned?

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